

DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEES' JOB SATISFACTION: THE REVIEW OF MANAGEMENT AND PROFESSIONAL OFFICERS IN DEWAN BANDARAYA KUALA LUMPUR (DBKL)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the determinants that influence the level of job satisfaction and the relationship on work environment, payment, promotion opportunities, supervision and nature of job towards job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL. The population was selected due to the diversity of the officer's group, particularly in terms of age, gender and race. The stratified sample size of 217 respondents were collected through questionnaires. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 26.0. The collected data were tested and analyzed using descriptive analysis, reliability testing, multiple linear regression, Pearson correlation coefficient analysis and one-way ANOVA. Findings have shown a significant, positive and strong relationship between all the independent variables and the dependent variable. DBKL as a local authority for the capital city of Malaysia may use this study as a reference in order to make the right decision towards job satisfaction among the employees. In addition, the study impacts the future performance of the organization by taking all the factors that influence job satisfaction more seriously within their organizations to increase the motivation and commitment level of their employees. In a conclusion, the top management may relook and further improve aspects that influence the job satisfaction, design better work policies and provide a conducive work environment to enhance job satisfaction as well as performance and productivity of the employees.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Working Environment, Payment, Promotional Opportunities, Supervision and Nature of Job, Management and Professional Officers, Dewan Bandaraya Kuala Lumpur (DBKL)

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is an individual's subjective view of their feelings about their job and organization. Job satisfaction will produce a pleasant emotional state and provide achievement to the employee's job value (Courtney & Younkyoung, 2017). According to Beyene (2020) study on

factors that determine the employee's job satisfaction in public sector is very crucial because their service quality and performance highly affect the economy of the country.

Asar-ul-Haq et al., (2017) pointed that job satisfaction is the primary indicator of organizational and employee effectiveness and performance in corporate and industrial settings. Organization needs to continuously ensure that their employees' job satisfaction is at a decent level by carrying out some work one love, enjoy and being compensate for one's undertakings in order to increase job satisfaction. Therefore, it can help the organization to produce employees with a better job performance (Zakaria et al., 2016). Employees' job satisfaction has the strongest influences on the public sector's service quality in providing services to the internal and external customers (Hamli et al., 2018). The role and commitment of the middle management level is also very important in ensuring the implementation of quality management, work process improvement and customer service in public service organizations (Alhaqbani et al., 2016).

Towards the vision to be a world-class city, the DBKL must face a challenge to managing their stakeholder and the employee to achieve the DBKL's mission. Having talented, skillful, competent, and knowledgeable employees in an organization is essential. In this way, the satisfaction of these qualified workers is a need in DBKL

In line with readiness for future challenges, DBKL's role as the local authority of Malaysia's capital city need to be equipped with a strong financial position, visionary leadership, strategic planning and a supportive support system. DBKL is not exempt from receiving complaints in carrying out its duties and responsibilities. Employee's job satisfaction has the strongest influences on the public sector's service quality in providing services to the internal and external customers (Hamli et al., 2018). Khalil-Ur Rahman et al., (2017) pointed that customer satisfaction is important in the service of every organization, however dissatisfied employees will have a negative impact on the services delivered in turn negatively impact external customer satisfaction. Levels of employee job dissatisfaction can lead to decreased productivity and employee morale.

Renyut et al., (2017) conclude government agencies as a non-profit organization that need to enhance the employees' commitment and ensure the employee's competency in order to satisfy them and increase their performance and functions. By understanding the level of job satisfaction, employer of DBKL will understand how the stated variables will influence the employee's job satisfaction level. Hence, it is necessary to satisfy their work employee since they are the asset of the organization to avail all these successes as the employees have direct interaction with the customer and represent their organization. In other words, to increase the organization's outcome, the employer needs to satisfy their employees in the first place (Nurjalilah, 2020).

With this background, this study is to assist the top management of DBKL to develop a strategic planning action in ensuring the job satisfaction level among management and professional officers is always high. This study will enable the top management of DBKL to understand how the stated variables will influence the employee's job satisfaction level and provide knowledge for others. The DBKL's top management must take vital steps to retain satisfaction of their employees and other variables related to the performance of organizations. It is crucial to figure out the impact of all these variables on employee's job satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the main leader of organizational and employee effectiveness and performance in corporate and industrial settings (Asar-ul-Haq et al., 2017) and the satisfied workers are committed towards their institutions committed, and boosts productivity, increases work engagement, creates a sense of belonging, injects creativity and innovation, lowers the turnover rate, and has many more positive impacts. (Robbins et al., 2012; Malik et al., 2017). Job satisfaction is also an individual's subjective point of view encompassing how they feel about their job and organization. It also helps the organization maintain a harmonious and conducive working environment, and its vital is undeniable (Yousef, 2017).

Work Environment

The work environment proved to be the most influential and produced significant job satisfaction among the employees where the employees were able to acquire a comfortable physical work environment; of course, the feeling of fun to work would come naturally (Rashid et al., 2019). Working environment of an employee is one of the important indexes of measuring their working comfort and their satisfaction. The peaceful working environment has an influence on employee performance that can cause a person to adjust his compatibility with the place of work; the physical environment consists of good ventilation and temperature, noise, lighting and facilities (Singgih et al., 2020).

A good work environment can increase employee motivation and satisfaction, which is essential for organizational performance as in the research of Hanaysha (2016). Employee job satisfaction plays the important role in the employees' feelings towards their jobs. Employees may bring a positive effect to the company if they meet job satisfaction. In other words, employees who are totally engaged with their work tasks are bursting with enthusiasm and passion to their jobs, absorbed in their work activities, open to new information, more productive, and more likely to go the extra mile. This indicates that driven and satisfied employees at work also have a great working environment and are committed to the company. It is critical to instill in employees a strong sense of belonging and a sense of family. To improve these elements, the organization must develop programs and events. (Manila Metro, 2020).

Payment

Salaries or payments within a specified period are cash compensation, provided by the employer for work performed by the employee, along with other gratuities referring to other benefit payments to the employee. Cash payments are basic payments related to hourly or weekly wages plus overtime pay, shift differences and fixed employee allowances while performance allowances such as promotions, salary bonuses, other government incentives and subsistence assistance if applicable according to interpretation by Suleiman et al., (2018). Finding study by Beyene (2020) job satisfaction is a function of how fairly a person is treated in the workplace. Employees want a pay system and promotion policy that they consider fair, clear, average and

in line with their expectations. Santoscoy (2019) noted that the government gave fixed monthly payments and long-term employment guarantees to public sector employees to motivate them to continue working in this sector. People prefer working in the public sector because of the payment, retirement, and health care benefits are highly related to employee motivation, especially those who are already married and have a commitment. Almost all authors have the same findings that payment has a major impact on the performance of jobs. The theory of Herzberg says wages are one of the payments and incentives to employee gets motivated. Motivation is linked to work performance directly. Herzberg's theory also emphasizes the importance of payment to motivate and produce employees (Alrawahi et al., 2020).

Promotional Opportunities

Promotional opportunities can be defined as the internal mobility within the organization by changing positions vertically. Many employees find that holding the same position and repeating the same daily tasks for many years is very tedious, but this can avoid that if the employee expects to gain promotion to a higher position with new tasks and responsibilities and the new environment within the organization (Abuhashesh et al., 2019). Tatar (2019) research have shown that satisfaction with work, satisfaction with payment and incentives, promotional opportunities for growth, progress and career advancement, satisfaction with the style of leadership and supervision, satisfaction with the work group and social relations between employees, and satisfaction with work conditions such as safety, health and stability, all these factors have shown very significant impact on the level of organizational commitment. The above factors are very effective in impacting job satisfaction and the organization should take serious attention to improve its application in the organization because it will directly have a positive impact on the organization in the future.

Supervision

Satisfaction with the performance appraisal process and good supervision significantly affect the overall job satisfaction of municipal government employees. This is supported by the study of Ellickson et al., (2018) listening to employees' suggestions and ideas for improvement enables employees to be authoritative and accountable for their jobs well. The highest levels of expectations for both groups occurred for good supervision by their supervisors (Blonski et al., 2018). Hence, employees' relationships at work with supervisors/peers, acknowledgement of their work, career development, career growth, rewards, working conditions, and organizational environment (work policies) significantly impact employees' job satisfaction as per Rahman et al., (2017) research. Employees who perceived strong support from organization may strengthen their management-employee relationship which leads them to feel comfortable with the workplace environment and improve their work performance such as service quality (Hamli et al., 2018).

Nature of Job

The nature of a job is defined as the type of work performed by the worker. Employees can include the nature of this job in the employee title. For example, a human resource manager is someone who manages the human resources department and performs all related tasks and is entrusted

to it. The employee will perform related work in accordance with his knowledge and ability (Salleh et al., 2020). The nature of the job itself becomes a dominant factor of job satisfaction when employees assess different aspects of their work, like supervision, growth opportunities, salaries, colleagues, etc. When the job performed by an employee is perceived to be important, this will increase satisfaction level (Beyene, 2020). Employees tend to prefer jobs which afford them the opportunity to apply their skills and abilities. Hence, it is important for managers to take innovative steps to make work more interesting in order to increase the levels of job satisfaction of employees. Individuals discovering that their jobs were meaningful will feel fulfilled from both job and life. They work in a job meeting their prospects and they have additional positive attitudes towards the job. The more workers are given self-determination in the workplace the more they experience job satisfaction (Mbhele, 2019).

Proposed Conceptual Framework

The framework of this research was constructed from literature reviews on the determinants of job satisfaction and supports the conceptualization of the objectives and research questions of this study. The proposed conceptual framework is shown in Figure 1. We identified five independent variables: work environment, pay, promotional opportunities, nature of job and supervision as the determining factors that influence employee's job satisfaction.

Figure 1 Proposed Research Framework

(Source: Beyene, 2020)

- H1: There is a significant relationship between the work environment and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL
- H2: There is a significant relationship between the payment and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.
- H3: There is a significant relationship between the promotional opportunities and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.

- H4: There is a significant relationship between the supervision and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.
- H5: There is a significant relationship between the nature of job and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.

Findings of previous research clearly show that all five independent variables in this research is environmentally unfriendly to the organization as it can adversely affect employees' job satisfaction. Job satisfaction that occurs among employees may cause them to be evaluated and categorized under underperformer. Hence, there is a likelihood that the unfavorable performance of these employees can affect the organization's efforts to achieve its goals. Previous research has evidence to substantiate the relationship between work environment, payment, promotional opportunities, supervision, nature of job and job satisfaction among employees in the organization especially in local authority. However, there were also studies which failed to prove this relationship. Due to inconsistency of research findings in this area as well as lack of research conducted in the public services sector, it is appropriate for researchers to consider this scope of study. This study focused on officers of government agencies in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

METHODOLOGY

The study used quantitative research design that included both primary and secondary data. Survey using questionnaire was used to collect research information. The data collection has been done through the distribution of questionnaires that have been verified to the targeted population in DBKL which consists of management and professional middle management officers from Grade 41 to 52 which is 521 out of 556 from total management and professional officers in DBKL. For this study, probability sampling was chosen instead of non-probability sampling. It was important to ensure the biasness is minimal; hence, simple random sampling was employed which also fulfill the generalization objective (Sekaran, 2016). Researchers have referred to the guidelines of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) and from the table, for a population of 521, a minimum sample of 217 should be selected.

The questionnaire that was used in this study was developed to measure the independent and dependent variables. The research instrument comprises three (3) sections: respondents' demography is in Section A, while Section B is are items for Job satisfaction and Section C includes items for work environment, pay, promotional opportunities, nature of job, and supervision. The questionnaire was distributed by using Google Form to target population among the DBKL officers. The data analysis tool used was Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS), version 26. In this research, a pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents to determine the reliability of the items for the variables well as identifying items that may to be improved or remove. Prior to the distribution of questionnaires to Management and Professional Officers in DBKL, the questionnaires were pilot tested done with 30 respondents from the target population. The pilot test data was tested, analyzed and generated using IBM SPSS software version 26. The following below is the results for the reliability test that was conducted prior distributing the questionnaire:

Table 1: Reliability Test Result for Pilot Test

Variables	No. of Item	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Reliability Description
Job Satisfaction (DV)	6	0.876	Good
Work Environment (IV)	7	0.891	Good
Payment (IV)	6	0.955	Excellent
Promotional Opportunities (IV)	5	0.916	Excellent
Supervision (IV)	5	0.945	Excellent
Nature of Job (IV)	5	0.836	Good

Based on the results from Table 1, job satisfaction, work environment and nature of job variables shows a good reliability range meanwhile the payment, promotional opportunities and supervision variables show an excellent reliability range (Edrak et al., 2013). From this result, the questionnaire no need to modification or rephrasing as all items are compatible and correlate well for each of them.

Out 521 questionnaires distributed, 248 were returned (47.6% response rate). The survey data was stored as a SPSS file and statistical analysis involves descriptive analysis, normality tests, Pearson's Correlation and Regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Summary of Respondents' Demographic

Variable	Classification Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Age	25 years old or below	1	0.5	0.5
	26-35 years old	54	24.9	25.4
	36-45 years old	117	53.9	79.3
	Above 46 years old	45	20.7	100
Race	Malay	214	98.6	98.6
	Chinese	-	-	98.6
	Indian	2	0.9	99.5

	Others	1	0.5	100
Gender	Male	128	59.0	59.0
	Female	89	41.0	100
Marital Status	Married	184	84.8	84.8
	Single	33	15.2	100
Work Position	Officers 52	32	14.7	14.7
	Officers 48	50	23.0	37.7
	Officers 44	75	34.6	72.3
	Officers 41	60	27.6	100
Department	Pejabat Datuk Bandar (Mayor of Kuala Lumpur)	2	0.9	0.9
	Pejabat Pengarah Eksekutif Perancangan (Executive Director of Planning)	2	0.9	1.8
	Pejabat Pengarah Eksekutif Pembangunan Sosio-Ekonomi (Executive Director of Socio-Economic Development)	1	0.5	2.3
	Pejabat Pengarah Eksekutif Pengurusan Projek (Executive Director of Project Management)	1	0.5	2.8
	Jabatan Undang-Undang dan Pendakwaan (JUP) (Legal and Prosecution Department)	7	3.2	6.0
	Jabatan Perancangan Korporat (JPRK) (Corporate Planning Department)	4	1.8	7.8
	Jabatan Audit Dalam (JAD) (Internal Audit Department)	2	0.9	8.7
	Jabatan Integriti (JIT) (Integrity Department)	3	1.4	10.1
	Jabatan Kewangan (JKEW) (Finance Department)	4	1.8	11.9
	Jabatan Pengurusan Sumber Manusia (JPSM) (Department of Human Resource Management)	8	3.7	15.6
	Jabatan Pentadbiran (JP) (Administration Department)	6	2.8	18.4

Jabatan Pengurusan Maklumat (JPM) (Information Management Department)	2	0.9	19.3
Jabatan Penilaian dan Pengurusan Harta (JPPH) (Valuation and Property Management Department)	18	8.3	27.6
Institut Latihan DBKL (IDB) (Centre of Excellence)	12	5.5	33.1
Jabatan Penguatkuasaan (JPK) (Enforcement Department)	11	5.1	38.2
Jabatan Pembangunan Komuniti dan Kesejahteraan Bandar (JPKKB) (Department of Community Development and Urban Wellbeing)	13	6.0	44.2
Jabatan Pelesenan dan Pembangunan Perniagaan (JPPP) (Department of Licensing and Business Development)	4	1.8	46.0
Jabatan Kesihatan dan Alam Sekitar (JKAS) (Department of Health and Environment)	4	1.8	47.8
Jabatan Kebudayaan, Kesenian, Pelancongan dan Sukan (JKKPS) (Department of Culture, Arts, Tourism and Sports)	2	0.9	48.7
Jabatan Pelaksanaan Projek dan Penyelenggaraan Bangunan (JPPPB) (Department of Project Implementation and Building Maintenance)	15	6.9	55.6
Jabatan Kejuruteraan Mekanikal dan Elektrikal (JKME) (Department of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering)	9	4.1	59.7
Jabatan Pembangunan Landskap dan Rekreasi (JPLR) (Department of Landscape Development and Recreation)	8	3.7	63.4

Jabatan Ukur Bahan (JUB) (Department of Quantity Surveyor)	14	6.5	69.9
Jabatan Kejuruteraan Awam dan Saliran (JKAWS) (Department of Civil Engineering and Drainage)	26	12.0	81.9
Jabatan Pengangkutan Bandar (JPB) (Department of Urban Transportation)	2	0.9	82.8
Jabatan Perancangan Bandaraya (JPRB) (City Planning Department)	16	7.4	90.2
Jabatan Perancangan Infrastruktur (JPIF) (Infrastructure Planning Department)	7	3.2	93.4
Jabatan Perancangan Ekonomi dan Pembangunan (JPEP) (Department of Economic Planning and Development)	10	4.6	98.0
Length of Services Less than 5 years	8	4.7	4.7
5-10 years	22	13.0	17.7
11-15 years	43	25.4	43.1
16-20 years	46	27.2	70.3
Above 20 years	31	18.4	100

Table 2 shows the percentage of respondents in their respective age group. As highlighted in the demographic analysis earlier, the highest number of respondents were in the age group of 36 to 45 years old with 117 respondents or 53.9 percent followed by age group of 26 to 35 years old with 54 respondents or 24.9 percent. Through the figure, we can see that majority are Malays (98.6%), 59 percent (128 respondents) were males majority (84.8%) married group. From the study, it is shown that 75 (34.6%) respondents are from group officers ranking in grade 44 which contribute the highest frequency, followed by group officers' grade 41 where 60 (27.6%) respondents take part in this study. While from the seniors' group, both were participated by the fraction of 50 (23.0%) from officers' grade 48 and 32 (14.7%) from officers' grade 52 respectively. From the respondents' department of duty demographic, the first three (3) highest departments were responding to the study are Jabatan Kejuruteraan Awam dan Saliran, Jabatan Penilaian dan Pengurusan Harta and Jabatan Perancangan Bandaraya where each of department dominate 26 (12.0%), 18 (8.3%) and 16 (7.4%). While the least departments who respond were Pejabat Pengarah Eksekutif Pembangunan Sosio-Ekonomi and Pejabat Pengarah Eksekutif Pengurusan Projek where each contribute only one (1) respondent or 0.5% as both departments only have a little number of officers. In terms of the length of services of the respondents in the DBKL organization, the largest score percentage group were from 11-15 years of service by 62 (28.6%) respondents, second largest from group 16-20 years of service by 51, followed by group above 20 years of service which contribute 46 (21.2%), while 39 (18.0%) were respondents from group 5-10 years of service and the lowest fraction is contributed

from group tenure of services less than 5 years which represent 19 (8.8%).

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Job Satisfaction	3.8886	0.60923	217
Working Environment	3.9901	0.60171	217
Payment	3.9324	0.72577	217
Promotional Opportunities	3.3456	0.80265	217
Supervision	3.9631	0.66703	217
Nature of Job	4.0323	0.55500	217

Based on the Table 3, all the mean of variables recorded are above 3.30.

Table 4: Reliability Analysis

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability
Job Satisfaction	6	0.901	Excellent
Work Environment	7	0.877	Good
Payment	6	0.964	Excellent
Promotional Opportunities	5	0.900	Excellent
Supervision	5	0.947	Excellent
Nature of Job	5	0.833	Good

The Cronbach's coefficient alpha values are between 0 and 1 and the higher values indicates greater reliability. Table 4 indicates that all Cronbach's coefficient alpha values are more than 0.7. Hence, the items are deemed to be a reliable for measuring each of the construct.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis

		Job Satisfaction	Work Environment	Payment	Promotional Opportunities	Supervision	Nature of Job
Pearson Correlation	Job Satisfaction	1.000					
	Work Environment	0.473*	1.000				
	Payment	0.552**	0.528	1.000			
	Promotional Opportunities	0.561	0.312	0.550	1.000		
	Supervision	0.510	0.546	0.399	0.383	1.000	
	Nature of Job	0.546	0.487	0.435	0.286	0.529	1.000

*p<0.05, **p<0.01

From Table 5, the analysis shows that there is a positive relationship between all variables.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.724 ^a	0.524	0.513	0.42519

Table 6 shows that the Multiple Regression Analysis returned a R Square value of 0.524. This indicates that 52.4 percent of the variance in the dependent variable is significantly explained by the independent variables of this model.

The Multiple linear regression model is formulated as follows:

$$\text{Job Satisfaction} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{WE} + \beta_2 * \text{PAY} + \beta_3 * \text{PO} + \beta_4 * \text{SUP} + \beta_5 * \text{NJOB} + \epsilon$$

Where WE=Work Environment, PAY=Payment, PO=Promotional Opportunities, SUP=Supervision, NJOB=Nature of JOB

Table 7: ANOVA Results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	42.023	5	8.405	46.489	0.000 ^b
	Residual	38.146	211	0.181		
	Total	80.170	216			

The ANOVA results in Table 7 shows that the regression model is significant ($F(5,211) = 46.489$, $p < 0.05$) at 5% significance level. This indicates that at least one of the independent variables is a significant determinant of Job Satisfaction.

Table 8: Coefficient Analysis

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.516	0.242		2.136	0.034
	Working Environment	0.082	0.064	0.081	1.286	0.200
	Payment	0.136	0.054	0.162	2.499	0.013
	Promotional Opportunities	0.240	0.044	0.317	5.429	0.000
	Supervision	0.124	0.057	0.136	2.173	0.031
	Nature of Job	0.300	0.065	0.274	4.596	0.000

The coefficient analysis indicates that if the p-value is greater than 0.05, it is considered as not significant while p-value that showed lower than 0.05 will be considered as significant. By looking at the Sig. column in Table 8, there were 1 variable where the p-value shows a value above 0.05, which is Work Environment with p-value of 0.200. This indicates that work environment was considered to have a not significant relationship with job satisfaction while payment, promotional opportunities, supervision and nature of job have significant relationship with job satisfaction.

Table 9: Summary of Hypotheses

No	Hypotheses	P-Value	Remark
H1	There is a significant relationship between the work environment and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.	0.200	Not Supported
H2	There is a significant relationship between the payment and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.	0.013	Supported
H3	There is a significant relationship between the promotional opportunities and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.	0.000	Supported
H4	There is a significant relationship between the supervision and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.	0.031	Supported
H5	There is a significant relationship between the nature of job and job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL.	0.000	Supported

Table 9 provides the summary to represent relationship of each variable being studied towards job satisfaction among management and professional officers in DBKL. The second to fifth hypotheses were supported because the p-value is less than 0.05, while the first hypothesis is not supported since the p-value was more than 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Job satisfaction has been perceived as a principal factor which is closely link with productivity of any organizational (Miah, 2018). According to Yin et al., (2017) the issue job satisfaction might affect the quality, productivity and sustainability of works. In this research, the factors which influencing job satisfaction among Management and Professional Officers in Dewan Bandaraya Kuala Lumpur become a major concern as it gives an impact towards productivity and performance in achieving organization's goals. Based on the result it shown a number of correlations between the independent and dependent variables.

Working Environment

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient value is 0.473, and it is significant at 0.000, which is less than the confidence threshold ($p < 0.05$). Based on the positive correlation coefficient, there is a positive relationship between working environment and job satisfaction. The result is consistence with Beyene (2020) who conducted a similar study in administration public sector comprising of 270 employees. As a result, job satisfaction is high when the working environment is good. The findings reveal that there is a direct relationship between the working environment and job satisfaction. This suggests that DBKL's management and professional officers are likewise concerned about the working environment in order to keep employees satisfied. H_01 will therefore be rejected and $H1$ accepted.

The working environment is one of the most important factors that influences employee satisfaction and motivation. In addition, a pleasant and supportive work environment is essential for job satisfaction (Agbozo et al., 2017). Working conditions such as noise, temperature, humidity, and light, according to Siti and Zahari (2006) have an impact on job satisfaction. Therefore, it is critical for the DBKL to provide a conducive working environment for its management and professional officers in order to ensure high productivity of their output.

Payment

Based on the result of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, the value is 0.552 and is significant at 0.000, which is less than the confidence threshold ($p < 0.05$), as shown in Table 4.13 in Chapter 4. The positive value for the correlation coefficient gives a positive relationship between payment and job satisfaction. When the reward and payment are high, there is a high level of job satisfaction. The findings reveal a moderate relationship between income and perks and job satisfaction. Management and professional officers in DBKL are therefore extremely concerned about the reward and payments in order to satisfy the organization. H02 will therefore be rejected and H2 accepted.

The most important factor influencing job satisfaction is wages (Mohammad et al., 2019). It is also supported by Thomas et al., (2019), that the annual income also became increasingly important to job satisfaction. When the pay is given according to the performance it tends to produce more promising results in terms of employee productivity and job satisfaction (Muhammad & Nawaz, 2017).

Promotion Opportunity

Based on the result of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, the value is 0.561 and is significant at 0.000, which is less than the confidence threshold ($p < 0.05$). The positive value for the correlation coefficient gives a positive relationship between promotion opportunity and job satisfaction. When the promotion opportunity is high it will significantly increase the level of job satisfaction. Management and professional officers in DBKL are therefore extremely concerned about the promotion opportunity in the organization. Therefore, H03 will be rejected, and H3 will be accepted.

According to Khalil-ur et al., (2017), acknowledgement of the employee's works, career development, career growth, rewards, working conditions, and organizational environment (work policies) have a significant impact on the job satisfaction of the employees. Muhammad and Nawaz (2017) suggest that for some people promotion is the key to job satisfaction and makes them feel that their status has improved which gives them power and satisfaction.

Supervision

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient value is 0.510 and is significant at 0.000, which is less than the confidence threshold ($p < 0.05$). Based on the positive correlation coefficient, there is a positive relationship between supervision and job satisfaction.

As a result, job satisfaction is high when the employee feels that the supervision to their works is great. The findings reveal that there is a direct relationship between the supervision and job satisfaction. Therefore, H04 will be rejected, and H4 will be accepted. The result was consistence

with Beyene (2020) that employees would expect supervision of their work, continuous basis supervision and support could generate satisfaction among workers of the organizations.

In addition, Yin et al., (2017) found that employees who are accepted, trusted, and valued by their supervisors and co-workers are more likely to contribute to their jobs, which had fully committed to the organization and thus, stayed loyal to the organization.

Nature of Job

Based on the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient value is 0.546, and is significant at 0.000, which is less than the confidence threshold ($p < 0.05$). The positive value for the correlation coefficient gives a positive relationship between nature of job and job satisfaction. When the employee effectively and efficiently in delivering their job, it can be associated with the high level of their job satisfaction. Therefore, H_0 will be rejected, and H_1 will be accepted.

According to Mine (2020) the workplace experiences and the emotional ability of the people are effective on job satisfaction. Generally, workload occurs when an employee has too much work and needs to be done in a certain period of time. Its occurrence causes pressure on employee who needs to overcome the inability (due to limited resources) to do the work. This phenomenon becomes a challenge for employees to perform their duties effectively and efficiently. It's supported by Mohd Salleh et al., (2020) that effectiveness and efficiency in performing jobs can be associated with job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

In overall, this research met its objective of investigating the determinants that influence job satisfaction among Management and Professional officers in DBKL. This research shows that the entire independent variables namely working environment, payment, promotion opportunities, supervision and nature of job has a significant impact on job satisfaction among Management and Professional officers in DBKL. The results supported all five hypotheses which indicate an important finding for the top managements as well as Human Resources Management Department (HRMD) and the entire level of the organization.

The findings validated the independent variables have a significant, positive and strong relationship with job satisfaction. The strong positive interrelation between variables tested on job satisfaction offer a wisdom way for organization to motivate, increase performance and productivity to achieve organization's ultimate goal as well as job satisfaction. On the other hand, the findings of this research are in line with affirmative of Herzberg's Motivation Theory (1967) regarding determinants of employee's job satisfaction.

With the understanding of the relationships between the factors and employee's job satisfaction, DBKL as a local authority for capital city of Malaysia will be able to make the right decision in ensuring job satisfaction among its employees. The management of DBKL may use it as a reference in order to increase job satisfaction among the employees. To ensure the employees could give their best for the organization, the organization as well as human resource practitioners have to focus on the aspects associated with job satisfaction.

Employees who are highly committed are also satisfied in their jobs, and vice versa. The findings of this study show that DBKL's Management and Professional officers are deeply committed to their organization, and that their high job satisfaction is a result of that commitment. High job satisfaction reflects genuine passion, positive feelings, and genuine devotion to the task, resulting in highly affective commitment (Sadiya & Maimunah, 2016). Hopefully, the findings of this study will serve as a model for other local governments in determining their employee's job satisfaction.

RECOMMENDATION OF FUTURE RESEARCH

Some recommendations were given in order to improve this study and overcome the constraints that it encountered. These suggestions can be considered by other scholars who are looking into this topic further. Firstly, to increase the sample size of the research. The larger of the sample size, the more accurate the results will be. Only the group of Management and Professionals officer level were focused in this research. So, for the future research in DBKL should be undertaken at various levels of employees to improve its significant and reliability of the data collected.

Having a larger sample size also will allow them to expand the scope of their research. In order to expand the significant factors that will influence the job satisfaction in DBKL, a preliminary observation or preliminary survey might be put into consideration to ensure that the preparation of questionnaires will be more comprehensive and covers various elements of human needs. Variables such as Human Resources Management (HRM) practice, empowerment and leadership may also become potential factors to influence job satisfaction among the employee which has not been covered in this research.

Future researchers may also add other variables which may affect the job satisfaction of employees, such as job involvement, professional commitment, and institutional citizenship. This research also can be extended towards other local authorities to compare the result in evaluating the most influential factors that contribute to job satisfaction among their employee. Thus, it able to accumulate the findings and observations towards the study on job satisfaction in other localities.

Data Availability

The data for this study is available upon request from the corresponding author.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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